

CARDIO WORKOUT FOR BEGINNERS ATHLETES – SAMPLE PROGRAM

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Abstract:

Cardio workout is an important part of the training plan of any athlete. It includes stretching exercises, workout on an exercise bike and treadmill. It requires special diet. During cardio workout recommended physical activity of moderate intensity.

Keywords: cardio, beginners athletes, sample program

1. Introduction

Lack of exercise and being overweight is a topical problem of modern society. Sports training contribute to the well-formed athletic, vitality, performance, self-esteem and good health. To achieve all this is necessary application of complex motor program and subject to certain principles in sports training.

2. Material and methods

Cardio training is an important part of the plan and should not be overlooked. For the beginner athletes objectives: reducing the percentage of body fat, improving the function of the cardiovascular and respiratory system, to improve blood circulation, leading to a better performance of the muscles, reducing stress, enhancing stamina,

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improves the condition of the body and improving the quality of life. It is also an essential tool for the prevention of osteoporosis and reduce the risk of diabetes.

2.1 Principles of the training

The most effective time for cardio is in the morning on an empty stomach. This is due to the low content of glucose in the blood and muscle glycogen. During the morning the training on an empty stomach increases the metabolism for the day. Indicating that morning cardio workout accelerates fat loss throughout the day. Cardio should be done 3 to 5 times a week between workouts, should not have more than 48 hours rest, because is not effective. The determination of the maximum heart rate is a key moment for the determination of physical exertion. Most often, it is theoretically calculated by the formula: $HR_{max} = 220 - \text{age}$. The most accurate determination of the individual maximum heart rate and hence correct dosage of physical exercise can be done based on maximum step up test on treadmill. This approach is especially recommended when the exercise with high intensity. The right intensity of training is the most important parameter. Novice athletes should start with low intensity, with about 55% of maximum heart rate to get used to the load. Gradually, the physical load increases until a moderate intensity (60-75% of maximum heart rate). Duration varies between 15 and 60 minutes, depending on the training experience and goals of the trainee. Cardio consists of preparatory, primary and final part.

A. Preparatory part

Preparatory part involves stretching exercises for all muscle groups. The best way of warming up is to start with static stretching. This is gradually stretching to reach a certain point in one direction, which felt a slight tightness but no pain. Hold for seconds/5-7 seconds/, then the exercise is performed in another direction. The duration of the preparatory part is 5 minutes.

B. The main part

Workout on Treadmill. The intensity of physical activity is a function of the speed of the path and its slope. At the beginning of the load is of low intensity (about 3 MET - with 3 km / h in equal parts). Reaching the target intensity becomes stepwise by every 2 minutes the speed is increased by 1 km/ h. After reaching a speed 5 km/h intensity is increased by increasing the slope of the path. The intensity is reported in MET, while reaching the target load stays within the predetermined duration. In subsequent weeks increase the load by about 0.3 to 0.5 MET. Workout exercise bike. The load starts to 25W, as every 2 min. Increases with 25W (step load). Upon reaching the target load stays within the predetermined duration.

C. The final part

It involves stretching exercises for all muscle groups. The final part lasts 10 minutes.

3. Results

Presented program is very well tolerated by novice athletes not associated with complications and improve their quality of life.

Table 1: Groups receiving our example program for beginner athletes and a control group

	Experimental group Control group	Control group (in the begining) Control group (after 30 days)	Experimental group (in the begining) Experimental group (after 30 days)
Z	-3,508(a)	-2,877(a)	-2,877(a)
Asymp. Sig.(2- tailed)	,002	,004	,0001

Statistical data processing (tab. 1) by Wilcoxon Signed Ranks Test ($\alpha = 0,0001$, $\alpha = 0,002$ and $\alpha = 0,004$), shows that groups receiving our example program for beginner athletes and a control group that was not applied methodology. They are homogeneous. The differences observed in the data at the beginning and end of the experiment were statistically significant. The applied methodology significantly improves quality of life and helps fast restoration of motor activity against a normalized muscle tone. This is done by using special exercises for the lower limbs and muscles supporting the dorsal flexion of the foot on treadmill.

4. Discussion

To achieve better sporting achievements require regular application of physical activity and the basic principles of cardio workout. This program helps improving the function of the cardiovascular and respiratory system, to improve blood circulation, leading to a better performance of the muscles, reducing stress, enhancing stamina, improves the condition of the body and improving the quality of life.

5. Conclusion

Cardio affect any age group and because of this, each exercise should be individually tailored with the specific needs of novice athletes.

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Bibliography

1. Gavriyski.V, Stefanova. D Kisselkov. E. II. Gavriiski. C. Human Physiology with physiology of sport. New knowledge Sofia 1998
2. Ivanova. K. Kasparian. H. The terms "Normal," "ideal," "Do," "healthy" body weight. *Massage Therapy and Rehabilitation* 2009 1-2. 5-12.
3. Karaneshev. D. Medical gymnastics at someone - common diseases. *Medicine and Physical Training*. Sofia 56-57 1975
4. Karaneshev. D. Theory and methods of Physiotherapy Sofia 1991.
5. Popova. D. Megova. T Cardio-vascular and respiratory dysfunctions. Popov N. Introduction to kinesitherapy. Sofia - PRESS NAV. 231-232. 2009

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